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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

O'quvchilarni intellektual rivojlantirishning psixologik omillari.....	22
<i>Ashurov Ramzidin Ramazonovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda bolaning kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishda oila bilan ishlashning nazariy asoslari	27
<i>Jumanova Fatima Uralovna, Allaberganova Munisa Begimboy qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanishning metodologik asoslari	32
<i>Jo'rayeva Nargiza Tairovna, Bekbergenova Yulduz Tanirbergen qizi</i>	
Faoliyatli yondashuv asosida maktabgacha 6-7 yoshli bolalarda nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	35
<i>Ziyodullayeva Mohirabonu Ikromjon qizi</i>	
Davlat ta'lim muassasalarida manfaatlar to'qnashuvini boshqarishning tashkiliy-huquqiy mexanizmlari ...	39
<i>Xaybatullaeva Sojidxon Ziyatullayevna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida jismoniy tarbiya darslarining samaradorligini oshirishda integratsion yondashuv	42
<i>Kamoliddinov Mirzohid</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishda interfaol metodlarning samaradorligi	45
<i>Kamoliddinova Dilnoza Axmadilaxanovna</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda kreativ faollikni rivojlantirish mexanizmlari.....	48
<i>Nurjanova Rayxan Urazbaevna</i>	
Sinf biologiya fanini o'qitishda TIMSS topshiriqlardan foydalanish metodikasi va baholash mezonlari	52
<i>Xaitboyeva Dilorom Rustam qizi</i>	
Qandli diabet tashxisli bemorlarda shaxs tuzilmasining emotsional komponentlari	56
<i>Sadikova Umida Botirovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda pedagogik diagnostikani amalga oshirishning natijaviyligi	60
<i>Maxmutazimova Yulduz Raxmatovna, Qodirova Shaxnoza Saidazim qizi</i>	
Kasbiy imij shakllanishida psixologik jihatlarning tafovutlari	64
<i>Aminova Dilnoza Orifjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari direktorlarining jamoa bilan ishlash jarayonida yetakchilik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish	69
<i>Abdiyeva Fazilat Fayzulla qizi</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalar shaxsi rivojlanishida psixologik moslashuvning tipik xususiyatlari	73
<i>Mirsaitova Guzal Baxodirovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida variativ modellashtirish asosida talabalarning kreativ faoliyatini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarining qo'llanilishi	76
<i>Quvvatova Mohira Hikmatillayevna</i>	
Interfaol treninglar orqali o'qituvchilarning innovatsion fikrlashini rivojlantirish tajribasi	79
<i>Abdiyeva Shodiyona Yodgor qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda milliy qadriyatlar asosida axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirishning ahamiyati.....	82
<i>Zulayxo Nazarova, Qarshiboyeva Muxlisa Ismatullo qizi</i>	
Ijodiy qobiliyatni o'stirishda pedagogik mahorat va innovatsion metodlar	85
<i>Mutallibova Odinaxon Mirzaolimjon qizi</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida olimpiadalarga tayyorlashda masalalar yechish texnologiyasi 11-sinf misolida	89
<i>Aslonov Xayrullo Shukrullo o'g'li</i>	

Bokschi qizlarni texnika taktikasini takomillashtirish.....	94
<i>Axmedov Latifjon G'ayrat o'g'li</i>	
Ixtisoslashtirilgan terminologiyaning asosiy lingvistik xususiyatlari	99
<i>Axmedova Dilnoza Anvarovna</i>	
Interfaol metodlar orqali zamonaviy darslarni tashkil etishning o'ziga xos tendensiyalari.....	102
<i>Bakirov Otabek Bo'ranovich</i>	
Boshqaruv psixologiyasi terminlarini tarjima qilishning metodologik muammolari	106
<i>D. J. Norboyeva</i>	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalari ruhiyatiga virtual muhitning salbiy ta'siri.....	110
<i>Giyosov Ulug'bek Eshpulatovich, Turayeva Nigora Husniddin qizi</i>	
Hamshiralik ishida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning samaradorligi.....	113
<i>Rasulova Gulmira, Amonova Dildora, Abdurahmonov Aziz, Hakimova X. X.</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kognitiv qobiliyatlarni shakllantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar	117
<i>Jumayev Xushboq Soatmumin o'g'li</i>	
Principles of Organising Autonomous Learning.....	121
<i>Khazratova Zukhra Mamaraimovna</i>	
Najot – ta'limda, najot-tarbiyada	124
<i>Mo'minova Manzura Mamasodiqjonovna</i>	
Educational Potential of Museum Pedagogy and Criteria for its Application in Developing Historical Thinking of Pre-Service History Teachers.....	127
<i>Niyozov Javlonbek</i>	
Landshaft dizayni vastasida bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachilarining estetik va kreativ ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish	131
<i>Radjapova Zuxra Tirkashevna</i>	
Abdulla Avloniy pedagogik merosida shaxs psixologiyasi masalalari.....	134
<i>S. O. Mamarasulov, D. A. Egamberdiyeva</i>	
TBL metodini qo'llash orqali o'quvchilarning madaniyati va ijtimoiy muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish....	138
<i>Sodikova Oyshakhon Muxammadsodik</i>	
Pedagogik innovatsiyalarni boshqarishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	142
<i>Solihova Barno Sodiq qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim magistratura talabalarining ijodiy faolligini rivojlantirish shart-sharoitlari	146
<i>Yarmatov Shermo'min Rahmatovich</i>	
Формирование готовности родителей детей старшего дошкольного возраста к выполнению воспитательной функции в семье.....	149
<i>Атаджанова Сохиба Талиповна</i>	
Redjio pedagogik yondashuv asosida maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda mantiqiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	152
<i>Djamilova Nargiza Nuritdinovna, Otahonova Marjona</i>	
Talabalarda algoritmik kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning sun'iy intellekt va Big Data Analytics asosida o'quv faoliyatini real vaqt rejimida kuzatuvchi va boshqaruvchi konseptual modelni takomillashtirish.....	155
<i>Kayumova Nazokat Rashitovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida chet tili o'qituvchilari va talabalar o'rtasidagi interaktsiyaning pedagogik samaradorligi va innovatsion mexanizmlari	163
<i>Eshonqulova Umida Xolmirzayevna</i>	
MTTlarda nutqni rivojlantirishga doir mashg'ulotlarda interfaol usullardan foydalanish texnologiyasi	168
<i>To'laboyeva Iqbolaxon Olimjonovna</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonidagi konfliktlar.....	173
<i>Abulova Mohigul Komiljonzoda</i>	
Talabalarining bolalarda ijtimoiy moslashuvni shakllantirishga kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish	176
<i>Inomova Mahliyo Yusuf qizi</i>	

Shaxs tuzilmasida ma'naviy intellekt: nazariy-metodologik tahlil va psixologik interpretatsiya	179
<i>Mirxoliqova Charos Xabibullaevna</i>	
18-20 yoshli belbog'li kurashchilarning musobaqa oldi jismoniy tayyorgarliklari	183
<i>Muzafarov Muxammadali Maxsudovich</i>	
Talabalarda mustaqil ta'lim topshiriqlaridan foydalanib kasbiy madaniyatini rivojlantirishga zamonaviy yondashuvlar (boshlang'ich ta'limda tarbiya fani misolida)	187
<i>Yadgarova Surayyo</i>	
Maktab o'quvchilariga pedagogik ta'sir ko'rsatishda o'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olish	190
<i>Yo'ldoshova Shahlo Shukurullo qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini ma'naviy-ma'rifiy faoliyatga tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishning nazariy tahlili	194
<i>Yusupova Sanobar Odil qizi</i>	
Типология научного текста: от жанровой классификации к дискурсивной модели	197
<i>Бахтияр Катибжанович Саттаров</i>	
Взаимодействие педагога и семьи в профилактике и преодолении стресса у детей дошкольного возраста	201
<i>Г. С. Алиходжаева, Х. Рахимова</i>	
Условия эффективности инклюзивного образования	206
<i>Г. С. Алиходжаева, Л. О. Бекмуродова</i>	
Педагогическая готовность к обучению в школе детей билингов	211
<i>Г. С. Алиходжаева, Н. А. Ганиева</i>	
Педагогические условия формирования эмоционального интеллекта у дошкольников	216
<i>Джалилова Феруза Намазовна</i>	
Milliy meros va musiqiy madaniyatning yosh avlod tarbiyasidagi o'rni	219
<i>Zuhriddin Azizov</i>	
Госпитальная школа как пространство поддержки и развития ребёнка (на примере госпитальной школы при детской клиники Синсиннати, США)	222
<i>Муминов Р. Р., Хакимова Н. Х., Набиева Г. Г.</i>	
Интерактивные формы работы в процессе профориентации детей дошкольного возраста	227
<i>Н. Т. Жураева, С. М. Ахмеджанова</i>	
Samarali hamkorlikdagi faoliyatga tayyorlashga oid yondashuvlar	231
<i>Hojiyeva Zulfiya O'ktamovna</i>	
Поэтапное вовлечение детей с расстройствами аутистического спектра в дошкольное инклюзивное образование: комплексный анализ научно-теоретических и практических подходов	234
<i>Сабина Рагимова Ровшан кызы, Айсель Масимова Арастун кызы</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida fizika fanini o'qitish metodikasini rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishni boshqarishni takomillashtirish	245
<i>Allaniyazova Bibigul Sarsenbay qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darslariga kreativ fikrlash asosida tayyorlash	248
<i>Botirova Jumagul Chori qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda fanlarni o'qitish metodikasini rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishni boshqarishni takomillashtirish	254
<i>Kaypova Gulnara Muratbaevna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonlik ko'nikmalarining rivojlantirish masalalari	257
<i>Davletova Hamida Xasan qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini ma'naviy axloqiy ruhda tarbiyalashning psixologik jihatlari	261
<i>Fayzullayev Ermat Majidovich, Ortiqova Mashxura</i>	
Orkestr va ansambllarning fan sifatidagi o'rni va tarbiyaviy ahamiyati	265
<i>Fayzullayev Ermat Majidovich</i>	
Maktab fizika darslarida interaktiv dasturlar va simulyatorlardan foydalanish metodikasi	269
<i>Xayriddinova Malikaxon Qodirxon qizi</i>	

Musiqada midi musiqiy cholg'ularning raqamli interfeysi.....	274
<i>Omonov Xasanxon Sulaymonovich</i>	
Karyera o'sishida gender tafovutlarning ahamiyati.....	277
<i>Yulchiboyeva Nazokatxon Iqboljon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak musiqa o'qituvchilarining kreativlik sifatlarini rivojlantirishga ta'sir etuvchi pedagogik omillar	283
<i>Omonov Xasanxon Sulaymonovich, Normuradova Nafisa Kuchkarovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ekologik tarbiyasi – ijtimoiy pedagogik muammo sifatida	287
<i>Kasimova Dilrabo Baxadirovna, Marjona Atoyeva Ismat qizi</i>	
Ilk yoshdagi bolalar psixologiyasi va rivojlanish xususiyatlari.....	291
<i>Kayumova Nargiza Mirziyatovna, Ne'matjonova Gulzira Ne'matjon qizi</i>	
Jadid pedagogik tafakkurida "o'qituvchi" fenomeni.....	294
<i>Xushbokov Oybek Uralovich</i>	
Maktabga tayyorlov guruhi tarbiyalanuvchilarida savol berish malakalarini shakllantirish	296
<i>Erhanova Nasiba Absayitovna</i>	
Musiqiy ta'limda xalq va zamonaviy qo'shiqlar vositasida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning etnomadaniy komponentlarni shakllantirish	298
<i>Qurbanova Muslima Shavkatbek qizi</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablari o'quvchilarida tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalarini tarkib toptirish metodikasi (biologiya fani misolida).....	300
<i>Akmalova Farida Dilmurod qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda adaptiv ta'lim texnologiyalari yordamida bolalar ijodkorlik ko'nikmasini shakllantirish mazmuni.....	304
<i>To'xliboyeva Zuxra Abdumutal qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi iqtidorli bolalar bilan ishlashda ta'lim texnologiyasi	308
<i>Xudoyberdiyeva Durdona Baxodir qizi</i>	
Pedagogik-psixologik qarashlarda otaning oiladagi o'rni haqidagi tasavvurlarni shakllantirish dinamikasiga oid fikrlar talqini.....	311
<i>Karshiyeva Dilafuz Suyunovna, Maxamatova Munisa Mamirzo qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga ingliz tilini o'qitishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari	314
<i>Axmatqulova Maxfuza Shuhrat qizi</i>	
Integrativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda interpersonal intellekt ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish ...	318
<i>G'ulomova Oychehra No'monjon qizi</i>	
Etnomadaniy qadriyatlarni integratsiyalashgan ta'lim jarayonida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga singdirishning samarali yo'llari	321
<i>G'ulomxo'jayeva Mushtariy Elmurod qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida grafik organayzerlardan foydalanish	324
<i>Iroda Isroilova</i>	
Buxoro iqlimi va tabiiy resurslaridan samarali foydalanish: ekologik va fizik-geografik yondashuv	329
<i>Mardonova Saodat Muzaffarovna</i>	
Effective Traditional and Innovative Approaches in English Language Teaching: Evidence From EFL Classrooms	333
<i>Yuldoshev Khaydarbek</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining lug'at boyligini rivojlantirishda lingvopedagogik yondashuvning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	336
<i>Allayarova Sojida Umirzakovna</i>	
Механизмы использования цифровых педагогических технологий для обеспечения непрерывности образовательного процесса учащихся начальных классов в условиях длительного лечения	339
<i>Турсунова Д. З., Холлиева Н. Х.</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'tkazilgan o'yin faoliyatlarini bolalar ovozi talaffuzining takomillashuviga ta'siri	342
<i>Kattaxo'jayeva Shaxlohon Bohodirovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	O'qituvchilar tayyorlashda pedagogik innovatsiyalar va milliy kontentni integratsiya qilish strategiyalari ... 344 Rahmatova Feruza Qudrat qizi	344
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlash jarayonini tashkil etishda tizimli yondashuv 348 Abdusamatova Nargiza Jamoliddinovna	348	
Moliyaviy savodxonlik asoslarini shakllantirish uchun "Tejamkor bola" o'yinli ta'lim faoliyatini asosida ishlashni takomillashtirilish..... 352 Rizayeva Munisxon Maxkamovna	352	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida byudjet hisobi standartlariga (BHS) muvofiq buxgalteriya hisobini tashkil qilish va yuritish tartib-qoidalari..... 356 Boltayev Ahmad Rustamjonovich	356	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari moliyaviy munosabatlarning huquqiy asoslari 359 Boymuradov Normurod Abdusadikovich	359	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya va sportni rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari..... 362 Ma'rufov Mansurbek Musajonovich, Xonimov Mirqosim Samatqul o'g'li	362	
O'smirlarda liderlik xususiyatlarini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari..... 367 Salayeva Dilafuz Buranovna	367	
Pedagog nutq madaniyatining milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga ta'siri..... 370 Toshtemirova Nigina Normurod qizi	370	
Новые методы обучения устному переводу студентов-переводчиков..... 373 Уринбаева Дилдора Утепбергеновна	373	
O'quvchilarda axborot iste'moli madaniyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik tuzilmasi 376 Muxammadiyev Baxtiyor Jurayevich	376	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'quvchilarning o'qish savodxonligini xalqaro mezonlar asosida rivojlantirish yo'llari 380 Axrorov Voris Yunusovich, Botirova Ozoda Nasir qizi	380	
Ta'lim sifatini baholashda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning o'rni (oliy ta'lim misolida) 385 Axrorov Voris Yunusovich, Boltayeva Jaxona Ulug'bek qizi	385	
Umumta'lim maktablarida 7-sinf biologiya fanini o'qitishda virtual laboratoriyalardan foydalanishning ta'lim samaradorligiga ta'siri 389 Turakulova Mehriniso Nuriddinovna, Ruziqulova Nilufar Abdumajidovna, Allanzarova Natalya Aleuatdinovna	389	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni maktabga tayyorlashning mavjud holati va rivojlantirish strategiyalari ... 393 Mamadaliyeva Mumtozbegin	393	
6–7 yoshli bolalarning bilim olishga faol qiziqishini rivojlantirish metodikasi 396 Artikova Muhayyo Botiraliyevna, Abduxolisova Gulsanam O'ktambek qizi	396	
The Main Peculiarities of Abbreviations in Modern English..... 399 Absalomova Aziza Baxodir qizi	399	
Autizmli bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlashda bir qator terapiya va metodlardan foydalanish 404 Yoqubova Hurriyat Burxonovna	404	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'yinlar, virtual reallik va geymifikatsiya orqali o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshirish..... 407 Xaitova Nazokat	407	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda tabiiy materiallardan foydalanishning pedagogik usullari..... 411 Rustamova Manzura Mirkamalovna, Qo'ziyeva Umriniso Muzaffar qizi	411	
Bo'lajak muhandislarning loyihalash ko'nikmalarini klaster muhitida rivojlantirish modellari 415 Eshonqulova Shafoat Ergashevna, Sherzod Eshonqulov	415	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotini rivojlantirish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqish 420 Ermatova Mamlakat Qadirkulovna	420	
9-sinf o'quvchilarini kasbga yo'naltirishda iqtisodiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida..... 423 Eliboyeva Lola Sulaymonovna	423	

Texnologiya asosidagi ingliz tili o'qitish va o'quvchi mustaqilligi: farmatsevtika talabalari misolida	427
Ikramova Shohsanam Ravshanboy qizi	
Maqollar asosida ingliz tili o'qitishning lingvodidaktik asoslari (Afg'oniston dariy tilli maktablar misolida) ..	430
Samadi Nooria	
Loyihaga asoslangan ta'lim texnologiyasi orqali talabalarda ijtimoiy mas'uliyat kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish tadqiqi	434
Jo'rayeva Zebiniso Yo'ldoshevna	
Boshlang'ich sinfda tabiiy fanlarni o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishda innovatsion va zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	440
Yulchiyeva Zulfiya Baxodir qizi	
Shaxsning individual intellektual rivojlanishi pedagogik muammo sifatida	444
Oltiboyeva Kamola Sharofjon qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'yin texnologiyalaridan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilar qiziqishini aniqlash yo'llari ...	448
Qalandarova Yulduz G'ayrat qizi	
Проблемы физического воспитания студентов и пути их решения.....	454
Ходжанов Азиз Рахимович	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda axloqiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda milliy ertaklardan foydalanish texnologiyasi.....	458
Kayumova Nargiza Mirziyatovna	
Jamiyatda sog'lom turmush tarzini tashkil qilishda jismoniy tarbiya va sport mutaxassislarining o'rni.....	461
Dehqonova Mahmuda Ortiqovna	
Yadro itqitish sport turida kuch tayyorgarligining biomexanik va funksional ahamiyati.....	466
Djabbarov Axror Islomovich	
Kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining didaktik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish.....	469
Axmedova Laylo Baxtiyor qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tayanch kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan strategiyalar.....	475
Urazimbetova Aygul Aralbayevna	
Eshitishida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda kompyuter texnologiyalarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari	482
Kamolova Yulduzxon Ma'murjon qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlarni tashkil etishda ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikni amalga oshirish texnologiyasi.....	488
Kasimova Dilrabo Baxadirovna, Jo'rabayeva Nozima Bekmurod qizi	
Psixologik zo'ravonlik oqibatlarini bartaraf etishda psixokorreksion mexanizmlar.....	491
Tursunpo'latova Zaxro Zafar qizi	
Shifokorlar professional karerasi resurslari va ularning obyektiv ko'rsatkichlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganish natijalari.....	496
Arziqulov O'tkirbek Maxammatovich	
Bolalarda maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi kommunikativ qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishda ijodiy o'yinlarning o'rni	501
Berdiyeva Umida G'oyibberdiyevna	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning neyropedagogik yondashuvlar asosida kognitiv rivojlantirishning mohiyati.....	505
Aliyeva Odila Madamin qizi	
Emotional Intelligence and Perceptive Ability: Keys to Pedagogical Success	508
Abdurakhimov Shokhasim Abdurakhmonovich	
Bo'lajak logopedlarni og'ir nutq nuqsonli bolalar bilan ishlashga tayyorlashning nazariy asoslari	511
Achilova Sevara Djasirkulovna	
Abdulla Avloniy pedagogik g'oyalarini zamonaviy boshlang'ich ta'lim bilan integratsiyalash	515
Daliyeva Eliza Zokir qizi	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	<p>Talabalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatlarni rivojlantirishda Mahmud Qoshg'ariy merosidan foydalanish..... 519 Eliboyeva Lola Sulaymonovna, Ravshanova Sarvinoz O'ktamjon qizi</p> <p>Derivation and Nominalization in Medical Terminology: A Comparative Model of Term and Process Name Formation in English and Uzbek 523 Gulnigor Yazdonkulova</p> <p>Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning nutq buzilishlarida pedagogik-psixologik korreksiya usullari hamda mexanizmlari..... 526 Jo'rayeva Muattar Abdumajit qizi</p> <p>Ta'lim sifatini boshqarishga tizimli yondashish hamda pedagogikada PDCA modelining ahamiyati 530 Jumanazarova Gullola Yoqubjanovna, Xolmatova Maftuna Turdimat qizi</p> <p>Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi ta'lim vositalarining kimyo ta'limidagi o'rni..... 535 Jumaniyazova Mahliyo Qahramonovna</p> <p>Inklyuziv maktab sharoitida kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-perseptiv tajribani shakllantirish ... 539 Karimova Zulfiya Abduraxmanovna</p> <p>Sirdaryo viloyati toponimlarining shakllanish jarayonlari 543 Kenjayeva Iroda Alisherovna</p> <p>Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlashda art texnologiyalardan foydalanishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari..... 546 Mamatova Husnora Eshquvatovna</p> <p>O'quvchi yoshlarning innovatsion fikrlashini rivojlantirish va uni amaliy faoliyat bilan integratsiyalash 550 Mehmonova Nilufar Shuhratovna</p> <p>Integrating Social-Emotional Learning in EFL Classrooms: Enhancing Language Proficiency and Emotional Intelligence..... 553 Meylinorova Feruza Bakhtiyor kizi</p> <p>Nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlari pedagog-tarbiyachilarining malakasini oshirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish 559 Muminova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna</p> <p>TEACCH konsepsiyasi – autizm va kommunikativ buzilishlari bo'lgan bolalarni davolash va o'qitish dasturi 562 Murodova Sarvigul Raxim qizi</p> <p>Aksiologik yondashuvlar asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarda altruizm ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning funksional modeli 566 Norboyeva Moxigul Shavkat qizi</p> <p>Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'yin texnologiyalari asosida bolalarning shaxsiy va ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarini takomillashtirish 569 Norqulova Ma'mura Husniddin qizi</p> <p>Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 6-sinfida o'qitiladigan "Tabiiy fanlar"dan mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish metodikasi..... 574 Qo'qonboyeva Shaxlo Rafikjonovna</p> <p>The Intersection of Science and Pedagogy: The Teacher's Role in Professional Evolution 580 Rahimberdiyev Rustam Abdunasirovich, Shukurova Madina</p> <p>Maktabgacha katta guruhlarida STEAM texnologiyasi bilan tanishtirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari 583 Rakhimova Laylo Hamidjon qizi</p> <p>Hamshiralik ishida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning samaradorligi..... 586 Rasulova Gulmira, Amonova Dildora, Abdurahmonov Aziz, Hakimova X. X.</p> <p>Kurashchilarda muvozanat (balance) va ko'tarib uloqtirish texnikasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik 590 Shermatov Gulom Qaxxorovich</p> <p>O'qituvchi shaxsining o'zini o'zi rivojlantirishida akmeologik pozitsiyaning o'rni..... 594 Xaitov Abdukosim Abdulakim o'g'li</p> <p>Lego-qurilish, konstruksiyalash, robototexnika – STEAM ta'lim moduli sifatida 596 Xamroyeva Sitora Samadovna</p> <p>Raqamli jamiyatda o'smir yoshdagi o'quvchilarning huquqiy axborot olish madaniyatini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari 599 Xayrullayev Axror Aktam o'g'li</p>
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Maktabgacha ta'limda axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari yordamida ta'limiy o'yinlarni loyihalash va joriy etish	602
<i>Xikmatova Moxinur Amir qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda tabiiy fanlar orqali kognitiv qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish zamonaviy yechimlarini ishlab chiqish usullari	605
<i>Xolmo'minova Mohichehra Bahrom qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarning biologiyaga qiziqishini oshirishda innovatsion ta'lim metodlari	609
<i>Xudayberganova Madina Saotboy qizi, AbdIQodirov Murodxo'ja Alisher o'g'li, Nishanbayeva Arayim User qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida shug'ullanuvchi voleybolchi qizlarning musobaqa oldi jismoniy va psixologik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish metodikasi.....	612
<i>Xudoynazarova Sayyora Ravshanovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda milliy qadriyatlar asosida bolalarni axloqiy tarbiyalash texnologiyalari	618
<i>Yo'ldoshboyeva Gulmira Xushnudovna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktab seksiyasi uzunlikka sakrovchilarining jismoniy rivojlanganlik darajasi.....	621
<i>Zokir Akramov O'tkir o'g'li</i>	
Perseptiv qobiliyat: o'qituvchining o'quvchini tushunish sa'nati.....	625
<i>Zokirov Mirzaraxim Abdaliyevich</i>	
Ожидания и потребности родителей как основа продвижения услуг дошкольного образовательного учреждения в Республике Узбекистан.....	628
<i>Ким Ирина Николаевна, Аббосхонова Зухра Баходир кизи</i>	
Экспериментальная деятельность – метод развития здоровьесберегающей компетентности у детей старшего дошкольного возраста	631
<i>Ким Ирина Николаевна, Алиходжаева Райхон Шавкат кизи</i>	
Подготовка детей-билингвов к школьному обучению: интеграция цифровых и традиционных педагогических методов.....	634
<i>Ким Ирина Николаевна, Умарова Шоиста Рустамовна</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim muhitida tarbiya tizimini takomillashtirishda interaktiv metodlarning o'rni.....	637
<i>Islamova Dilfuza Dilshodovna, Baymuratova Madina Baxodir qizi</i>	
Methodological Support of the Process of Developing Preschoolers' Cognitive Skills Through TRIZ (TIPS) in a Technology-Enhanced Learning Environment.....	641
<i>Gauxar Djanpeisova, Veronika Gorbunova</i>	
Innovative Approaches to Early Mathematics Education and Development in Preschool Children	646
<i>Gauxar Djanpeisova, Shaxodat Berdiyeva</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida intensiv texnologiyalar asosida mantiqiy tafakkurni rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	650
<i>Radjabova Mohigul Alisherovna</i>	
O'quv jarayonida ongli mushohada ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishda savol-javob usulidan foydalanish asoslari	653
<i>Ro'zimetova Intizor Alimovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari yozuv malakalarini shakllantirishning psixolingvistik tasnifi.....	656
<i>Axmataliyev Murodjon Ulug'bek o'g'li, Xojimatova Shoxsanam Erkinjon qizi</i>	
Ta'limda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining o'qituvchi kompetensiyasiga ta'siri	659
<i>Azamatova Rayhona Bahromjon qizi</i>	
13-14 yoshli o'quvchilarda harakatli o'yinlar va zamonaviy futbol mashg'ulotlarini integratsiya qilishning pedagogik asoslari	662
<i>Babayev Anvarjon Axmedovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish (nazariya, amaliyot va natijalar)...	666
<i>Berdiyev G'ayrat Ulaboyevich, A. N. Sadatova</i>	
Elektron portfoliolar asosida individual rivojlanishni monitoring qilishning diagnostik modeli.....	670
<i>Kopbayeva Baxtigul Ziyadinovna</i>	
Pedagogik atamalarning ta'lim jarayonidagi o'rni va ahamiyati	674
<i>Islomov Nurtoy Nomoz o'g'li</i>	
Abdulla Avloniyning axloqiy-ta'limiy qarashlari	678
<i>Abdullayev Muxammadimin Egamberdiyevich, Turg'unov Dostonbek Rustamjon o'g'li</i>	

Talabalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy ideallarni rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari	682
<i>Ziyotov Farrux Saodilla o'g'li</i>	
Nazorat qiluvchi pedagogik dasturiy vositalarni yaratishda sun'iy intellektning ahamiyati	686
<i>Ermonov Sherzod Ibrayim o'g'li</i>	
Kreativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak muhandislarda sog'lom turmush madaniyatini rivojlantirishning muhim yo'nalishlari	690
<i>Ibragimova Aziza Avaz qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'limda dual ta'lim va malakaviy amaliyotni takomillashtirish ("musiqqa ta'limi" misolida)	694
<i>Raximov Nurillo Narzullayevich</i>	
Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida musiqa san'atining shaxs ma'naviy-estetik tarbiyasidagi pedagogik ahamiyati	698
<i>Sattarov Alisher Alikul o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda multimediali mantiqiy masalalar orqali o'quv jarayonini faollashtirish.....	702
<i>Jamoldinova Dildora Alijon qizi</i>	
Ta'lim markazlarida o'quvchilarning nutq kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish metodologiyasi.....	706
<i>Buriyeva Xumoraxon O'lmasboy qizi</i>	
Raqamli jamiyatda o'smir yoshdagi o'quvchilarning huquqiy axborot olish madaniyatini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	710
<i>Xayrullayev Axror Aktam o'g'li</i>	
AI-грамотность будущих педагогов: компоненты, вызовы и педагогические стратегии этической интеграции искусственного интеллекта	713
<i>Наркабилова Г. П.</i>	
Роль психолого-педагогических факторов в формировании нравственного поведения дошкольников.....	718
<i>Рахматходжаева Ф. М.</i>	
Внедрение инновационных технологий в дошкольно-образовательном учреждении	721
<i>Садикова Шоиста Акбаровна</i>	
Para stol tennisi sportchilarida jismoniy tayyorgarlikni oshirish samaradorligi	726
<i>X. A. Usmonova</i>	
Systematic Approach to the Issues of Educational Calculation in General Secondary Schools	729
<i>Ajiniyazova Sholpan Saparniyazovna</i>	
Роль системного профессионального развития в формировании компетентности учителей английского языка: международные тенденции и практика Узбекистана.....	733
<i>Жамолитдинова Нилуфар Акрамжоновна</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf tabiiy fan darolarida funksional savodxonlikni rivojlantirish usullari	738
<i>Xujamkulova Nafisa Ruzikulovna, Saidmudova Maftuna Alisher qizi, Hafizova Oydiyoy Doniyor qizi, Xujamkulova Maqsuda Ruzikulovna</i>	
Ingliz tili darolarida Kahoot o'quv platformasidan samarali foydalanish	743
<i>Amankulov Shavkat Qudratovich</i>	
Bolalarning kognitiv qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda polisensor muloqot metodikasi	747
<i>Musratova Zilola Ulug'bekovna</i>	
Коммуникативные способности педагога – ключ к эффективному взаимодействию с учащимися.....	752
<i>Акрамова Л. Ю.</i>	
Искусственный интеллект в образовании: киберпедагогические стратегии развития критического мышления.....	756
<i>Сайфитдинов Ислombек Зоирович</i>	
Регион как фактор суицидального риска: от климата до культуры общения.....	761
<i>Султанова Амина Анваровна, Махсумова Зилола</i>	
Bo'lajak shifokorlarga anesteziologiya va reanimatologiya fanini o'qitishning nazariy asoslari.....	765
<i>Ismailov Oybek Abdurasulovich</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt (SI)ning kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishdagi metodik ahamiyati	768
<i>Komilov Furqat Solijon o'g'li</i>	
Implementing Total Physical Response Techniques in Your Language Class	770
<i>Rakhmatova Madina Sobirovna</i>	

Voleybolda holat va harakatlanish, yuqoridan va pastdan to'p uzatish texnikasi	772
<i>Sulaymonov Jaxongir Solijonovich</i>	
Методика формирования экологической культуры учащихся в процессе спортивного туризма	775
<i>Абдурахманов Отахон Рустамович</i>	
Методы преобразования и обработки текстовых задач в преподавании математики в начальных классах.....	780
<i>Азамкулов Ахтамкул</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari faoliyatida kreativ-tanqidiy fikrlash va muammoli ta'lim texnologiyalari integratsiyasining didaktik imkoniyatlari.....	787
<i>Jumayeva Muxlisa Shokir qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarni tayyorlashda kompetensiyaviy yondashuvning roli va ahamiyati .	793
<i>Yo'ldosheva Iqbol Bekbo'lsin qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf tarbiya darslarida jadid pedagogik merosidan foydalanish usullari	796
<i>Yusupova Madinajon Mansurbek qizi</i>	
Актуальность внедрения педагогики сотрудничества в современный учебный процесс на занятиях русского языка в группах с нерусским языком обучения	799
<i>Заболотина Анна Анатольевна</i>	
Loyihaga asoslangan ta'lim texnologiyasi orqali talabalarda ijtimoiy mas'uliyat kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish tadqiqi	802
<i>Jo'rayeva Zebiniso Yo'ldosheva</i>	
Alisher Navoiy asarlarida odob-axloq masalalarining falsafiy va tarbiyaviy talqini	807
<i>Ahadova Feruzaxon Akmaljon qizi, Usmonova Sofiyaxon</i>	
Globalashuv sharoitida ayollar ruhiy salomatligini saqlash va ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari.....	810
<i>Eshonqulova Guljahon Abduqaxxorovna</i>	
Tarbiyachi va pedagoglarning o'yin texnologiyalarini qo'llashdagi kasbiy tayyorgarligi hamda kommunikativ kompetensiyasi.....	814
<i>Xasanova Shaxnoza Toxtasinovna, Ostonova Marjona G'ulomovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda etnomadaniy kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda teatr texnologiyalarining qo'llanilishi	819
<i>Xasanova Shaxnoza To'xtasinovna, Sharobiddinova Shahzoda Doniyorbek qizi</i>	
Talabalarda agressiv xatti-harakatlar shakllanishining omillari	823
<i>Sa'dullayeva Aziza Iskandar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qish savodxonligi darslarida amaliy metodlar asosida kollaborativ va kommunikativ ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish.....	829
<i>Farsaxonova Mastura Jalol qizi</i>	
Jismoniy tarbiya va sport tadbirlarining ta'lim muassasalarida sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirishdagi o'rni	836
<i>Kimsanov Jamshidbek Maxamatrasul o'g'li</i>	
O'qituvchilarda kasbiy so'nishning profilaktikasi bo'yicha ijtimoiy-psixologik texnologiyalar	841
<i>Jamoliddinova Nigora Tohirjon qizi</i>	
Ta'limning raqamli modifikatsiyalari asosida talabalarning axborot mobilligini rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan pedagogik strategiyalar	846
<i>Xurramov Anvar Xudayshukurovich</i>	
O'zbek musiqiy merosining tarixiy-pedagogik rivojlanishi va zamonaviy ta'limdagi ahamiyati	853
<i>Yulyaxshiyev Sherali Narzullayevich</i>	
Учёт индивидуальных особенностей студентов национальных групп медицинского вуза в обучении русскому языку	857
<i>Мамаджанова Мохимир Рашидовна</i>	
Zamonaviy baholash texnologiyalari va xorijiy tajriba (boshlang'ich sinf "ona tili" darslari misolida).....	861
<i>A'zamqulova Zilola Sunnat qizi</i>	
STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasini boshlang'ich ta'limda qo'llashning me'yoriy-uslubiy asoslari.....	867
<i>Abdug'afforova Aziza Abdurashid qizi, Qudratova Shaxnoza Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Axborotni tanqidiy baholash asosida talabalarning mediasavodxonlik kompetentligini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	871
<i>Abdullajonova Nurzoda Nurmaxamadovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Harbiy xizmatchilar faoliyatida professional kuyish sindromining oldini olish 874 <i>Abdumalikova Iroda Abdulaziz qizi</i>
	Plifunksional yondashuv asosida maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari..... 879 <i>Abduraxmanova Mukaddam Mirsalikovna</i>
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyalashning pedagogik asoslari 883 <i>Barotova Huriyatxon Uzoq qizi</i>
	Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning konseptual jadval va grafik organayzerlardan foydalanish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish modeli 887 <i>G'ofurova Sh. M.</i>
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari direktorlarining kasbiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish zarurati 892 <i>Jovmirzayeva Nargiza Kuvondikovna</i>
	Talaba sportchilarning mashg'ulot yuklamalarini nazorat qilish xususiyatlari 895 <i>Matnazarov Anvar O'ktamovich, Jumonazarov Jaxongir Shixnazar o'g'li</i>
	Psixologik konsultatsiyada media ta'sirini inobatga olish zarurati 898 <i>Kuvandikova Gulnora Gulamovna</i>
	Soft Tissue Control: In the Aesthetic Zone 901 <i>Murodkulov Samandar, Narziev Firdavs, Buzrukhoda Javohir</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonlikni rivojlantirish mazmuni..... 905 <i>N. T. Misirova, Xursanova Mohinur Abduljabbar qizi, Ummatqulova Adashoy Baxtiyor qizi</i>
	Klassik ustoz–shogird an'analari va ularni innovatsion ta'lim usullari bilan uyg'unlashtirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari 910 <i>Raxmanova Nigora Xusanboyevna</i>
	Raqamli ta'lim muhitida talabalarning mustaqil ta'lim samaradorligini baholash usullari 914 <i>Shabdullayeva Lazokatxon Orifbekovna</i>
	Katta maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda emotsional intellektni tadqiq etishning nazariy-metodologik muammolari..... 918 <i>Shakirova Feruza Baxtiyor qizi</i>
	Talabalarni pedagogik dasturiy vositalarni loyihalashga mo'ljallangan web platformalarning imkoniyatlari 922 <i>Shamsutdinov Fazliddin Axmadovich</i>
	Talabalarda virtual jamoada ishlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning didaktik shart-sharoitlari..... 926 <i>Sodikova Odinaxon Abdugapporovna</i>
	Raqamli texnologiyalar vositasida o'quvchilarning mantiqiy va tanqidiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish modellari... 930 <i>Suyunova Nargiza Abdurashid qizi</i>
	G'ovlar orasidagi ritmik masofa tuzilishining sportchilarning musobaqadagi natijalariga ta'sirini tahlil qilish 934 <i>Talipov G'ulomojon Adiljanovich</i>
	Efficacy of a New Ointment for the Treatment and Prevention of Alveolitis..... 938 <i>Umarov Maruf, Abdurazzaqov Kamoliddin, Buzrukhoda Javohir</i>
	Tarbiyachi va pedagoglarning o'yin texnologiyalarini qo'llashdagi kasbiy tayyorgarligi hamda kommunikativ kompetensiyasi 941 <i>Xasanova Shaxnoza Toxtasinovna, Ostonova Marjona G'ulomovna</i>
	Oila muhitida ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya va uning pedagogik ahamiyati 945 <i>Yusupova Diloromxon Sabirdjanovna</i>
	6-7 yoshdagi bolalarni nutq o'stirish mashg'ulotlarida mustaqil fikrlashga o'rgatish 949 <i>Xabilova Sitora Tursunmurod qizi, Ziyadullayeva Madina</i>
	Local Anesthesia and Conduction Anesthesia 952 <i>Zulfiya Makhmudovna, Buzrukhoda Javohir</i>
	Современное состояние и проблемы подготовки педагогических кадров к инклюзивному образованию 957 <i>Плиева Руслана Владимировна</i>

EFFICACY OF A NEW OINTMENT FOR THE TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF ALVEOLITIS

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Abstract: A study was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of a newly developed ointment intended for the treatment and prevention of alveolitis. The ointment demonstrated a low risk of skin irritation while exhibiting high adhesive capacity, effective exudate absorption, and pronounced antiseptic properties due to its active components. The clinical trial involved 116 patients aged 25–60 years diagnosed with acute alveolitis, in whom the primary precipitating factors were exacerbations of chronic periodontitis and complex dental procedures.

Key words: alveolitis, treatment, ointment, dental surgery, periodontitis, antiseptic properties, wound healing, postoperative complications.

Annotatsiya: Alveolitni davolash va oldini olish uchun mo'ljallangan yangi ishlab chiqilgan mazning samaradorligini baholash maqsadida tadqiqot o'tkazildi. Maz teri tirnash xususiyati keltirib chiqarish xavfining pastligi bilan birga yuqori yopishqoqlik qobiliyati, ekssudatni samarali singdirish hamda faol komponentlari tufayli yaqqol antiseptik xususiyatlarga ega ekanligi bilan tavsiflandi. Klinik tadqiqotda 25–60 yoshdagi o'tkir alveolit tashxisi qo'yilgan 116 nafar bemor ishtirok etdi, ularda asosiy qo'zg'atuvchi omillar surunkali parodontitning zo'rayishi va murakkab stomatologik aralashuvlar bo'ldi.

Kalit so'zlar: alveolit, davolash, maz, stomatologik jarrohlik, parodontit, antiseptik xususiyatlar, yara bitishi, operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlilar.

Аннотация: Проведено исследование по оценке эффективности новой мази, предназначенной для лечения и профилактики альвеолита. Мазь характеризовалась низким риском кожного раздражения, высокой адгезивной способностью, эффективным поглощением экссудата и выраженными антисептическими свойствами благодаря активным компонентам. В клиническом исследовании приняли участие 116 пациентов в возрасте 25–60 лет с диагнозом острый альвеолит, у которых основными провоцирующими факторами являлись обострения хронического пародонтита и сложные стоматологические вмешательства.

Ключевые слова: альвеолит, лечение, мазь, стоматологическая хирургия, пародонтит, антисептические свойства, заживление раны, послеоперационные осложнения.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most common and challenging postoperative complications in outpatient oral surgery is alveolitis, also known as “dry socket” (alveolar osteitis). Depending on the complexity of the procedure and the patient's individual risk factors, the incidence of alveolitis after the extraction of permanent teeth, particularly mandibular third molars, ranges from 3% to 30%. The condition is characterized by intense radiating pain, delayed wound healing, and early dissolution of the intra-alveolar blood clot, which exposes the alveolar bone. These factors significantly impair the patient's quality of life and require multiple follow-up visits. Alveolitis has a multifactorial etiology that includes surgical trauma, bacterial fibrinolysis, and compromised local vascularization. Despite advances in surgical techniques, primary management of this condition still largely relies on local pharmacological intervention. Current therapeutic approaches include the use of various pastes or gels, analgesic dressings, and antiseptic irrigation. However, many commercially available treatments have limita-

tions, such as short duration of action, potential tissue irritation, or the inability to provide both comprehensive antibacterial and regenerative effects simultaneously.

In recent years, targeted topical formulations containing antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and osteoregenerative components have been developed to address these shortcomings. Ointment-based delivery systems are particularly advantageous in the oral cavity due to their mucoadhesive properties, which allow sustained release of active substances directly within the extraction socket. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the therapeutic effectiveness of a newly developed ointment intended for the treatment and prevention of alveolitis. The study aims to determine whether this novel formulation provides superior therapeutic outcomes compared to conventional treatment protocols by analyzing parameters such as pain reduction kinetics, the rate of granulation tissue formation, and prevention of secondary infection.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Among the most serious complications following tooth extraction are infectious processes affecting the bone wound and adjacent soft tissues (periodontitis, phlegmon), as well as neurological disorders and inflammation in the area of the extracted tooth (alveolitis). In this context, the search for effective methods for the treatment and prevention of these complications remains an urgent task in modern dentistry. Currently, several approaches are available for the treatment and prevention of alveolitis after tooth extraction. For postoperative recovery, allogeneic placental tissue may be used, shaped to match the size and configuration of the bone defect. This method accelerates healing and reduces the risk of alveolitis. Alternatively, hydrophobic ointments containing antiseptics or antibiotics (erythromycin, ditetracycline, gentamicin) are used for treatment and prevention. However, these methods present several challenges, including inadequate adhesion of medicinal substances to the socket walls, leading to rapid washout by saliva and blood, as well as pronounced local irritation. Within the framework of this research, the development and clinical validation of an ointment for the treatment and prevention of alveolitis were undertaken. The ointment is characterized by low local irritative activity while demonstrating high adhesion, sorption capacity, and antiseptic properties determined by the characteristics of its key components.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study included 116 patients aged 25 to 60 years diagnosed with acute alveolitis. During treatment, 124 teeth were extracted. The predominant factors contributing to the development of alveolitis were acute exacerbation of chronic periodontitis and the complexity of the extraction procedure. Patients were divided into two groups: the main group comprised 75 patients (60.4%), and the control group comprised 49 patients (39.6%). Patients in the main group were treated with a special ointment patented in Uzbekistan ("Ointment for the Treatment of Alveolitis"). The treatment protocol included local infiltration anesthesia, curettage of the affected area, irrigation of the socket with an antiseptic solution, and subsequent placement of the developed ointment into the surgical wound.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The composition of the ointment included anesthesin for local anesthesia, a hemostatic component, an antiseptic, beta-tricalcium phosphate, Solcoseryl Dental Adhesive Paste (registration number 015194/01-2003), and an ointment base consisting of lanolin and petrolatum. The incorporation of "Polysorb MP" into the ointment significantly enhanced its hemostatic properties. Solcoseryl Dental Adhesive Paste promoted rapid wound healing, provided analgesia, and protected damaged tissues; furthermore, it ensured reliable adhesion of the medicinal components to the walls of the extraction socket. Anesthesin, characterized by low toxicity, hypoallergenicity, and effective local anesthetic action, ensured patient comfort during the procedure. The lanolin-petrolatum base softened and stabilized the overall composition, contributing to its structural integrity. Beta-tricalcium phosphate accelerated regeneration and stimulated bone tissue formation. The components were mixed according to the prescribed formulation on a sterile surface and subsequently applied to the wound site, which was then covered with a collagen sponge. The ointment and sponge dissolved naturally within 3-4 days. In the control group, following anesthesia, the socket was curetted, treated with medications, and packed with iodoform gauze.

The treatment regimen also included sulfonamides, analgesics, and physiotherapeutic procedures (UHF therapy and microwave therapy). The effectiveness of the therapeutic intervention was evaluated based on patient-reported outcomes, the number of clinical visits, and radiographic findings in both short-term and long-term follow-up periods. The study results demonstrated that 68% of patients presenting in the acute phase of alveolitis experienced complete pain relief within 24 hours. By the end of the second day, a significant reduction

in hyperemia and mucosal edema in the area of the alveolar sockets was observed. No signs of inflammation were detected in the study group. Wound healing occurred by primary intention, and complete epithelialization was achieved within 4-5 days. In the control group, the resolution of inflammation and pain required a longer period, necessitating replacement of gauze turundas every 2-3 days, with a total of 3-4 changes. The average number of clinical visits per patient in the study group was 2.8, compared to 5.1 in the control group. A three-year follow-up of long-term outcomes demonstrated that patients in the study group did not develop alveolar ridge atrophy following tooth extraction.

CONCLUSION

Conversely, a moderate degree of atrophy was noted in the control group. The research results demonstrate the high efficiency of the proposed ointment compared to existing treatment methods. Due to its pronounced anti-inflammatory and regenerative properties, the ointment promotes rapid healing of bone tissues and prevents the development of inflammatory complications. Based on the data obtained, the developed ointment can be recommended as a promising tool for the treatment and prevention of alveolitis.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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